

MODELING OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM.

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Abstract: In this article, the supply of the cardiovascular system through a closed system, hemodynamic parameters and biomechanics of blood flow were studied in academic lyceum students. The obtained results from a mathematical model allow to evaluate the cardiovascular system.

Keywords: Systolic pressure, diastolic pressure, average blood pressure, heart beat volume, blood volume from the left ventricle, blood density, blood velocity in the aorta, heart work, heartbeat cycle, heart rate, minute volume of blood.

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The cardiovascular system provides blood circulation through a closed system of vessels. Continuous blood circulation in the body allows all cells to be supplied with necessary substances for their normal functioning and to remove their waste products. In order to carry out this important and very complex metabolic process in the capillaries, the cardiovascular system has certain functional and structural foundations. In this article, we will consider the biophysical basis of a number of processes occurring in the cardiovascular system.

Hemodynamic parameters of blood flow are determined by biophysical indicators of the entire cardiovascular system, i.e. internal characteristics of heart activity (for example, stroke volume), structural characteristics of blood vessels (their radius and elasticity) and properties.

Physical, analogue and mathematical modeling methods are used to describe a number of processes occurring in the circulatory system. Blood flow is considered both in normal conditions and in some disorders of the cardiovascular system.

The cardiovascular system is a self-consistent system with complex controversial opinions.

Hemodynamics is one of the branches of biomechanics that studies the laws of blood movement through blood vessels. The objective of hemodynamics is to establish the correlation between the main hemodynamic indicators, as well as their correlation with the physical indicators of blood and blood vessels. The main hemodynamic parameters include pressure and blood flow rate.

The main stages of modeling can include:

1. Primary collection of information.

2. Setting the issue.
3. Justification of basic assumptions.
4. Creating a model, studying it.
5. Checking the conformity of the model with the real object.

Mathematical models are built speculatively on the basis of experimental data (material or objective modeling) or using a hypothesis or known law (theoretical modeling). Theoretical modeling requires further experimental verification. Theoretical modeling is particularly useful in cases where experimentation is impossible or difficult.

The work is done by the heart mainly by the left ventricle. The work of the right ventricle is about 20% of the work of the left ventricle.

The work done with each contraction of the left ventricle is used to match the volume of blood ejected with the energy needed to move it throughout the vascular system. This energy consists of the potential energy of pressure, which must first be created to overcome the resistance to blood flow in the vascular system.

The statistical component of the work of the left ventricle is determined by the volume of the heart beat (V_y) and the average blood pressure in the aorta (P_o):

The amount of blood coming out of the left ventricle of the heart of the students is determined by the following formula.

$$A_1 = V_y \cdot P_o \quad (1) \text{ this } V_y \text{ -the systolic size of heart and}$$

$V_y = 100 + 0,5 \cdot (P_a) - 0,6 \cdot (P_d \text{ min}) - 0,6 \cdot (Y)$ (Starr) (2) it is determined by the following formula

$$V_y = 100 + 0,5 \cdot 35,8 - 0,6 \cdot 72,5 - 0,6 \cdot 16 = 64,8 \text{ ml , } Y \text{-age}$$

P_o -normal dynamic arterial pressure and $P_o = R_d \text{ min} + \frac{P_a}{3}$, (3). $P_a = P_s \text{ max} - P_d \text{ min}$ this P_a -the pulse pressure of heart, $P_s \text{ max}$ -the systolic pressure of blood, $P_d \text{ min}$ -the diastolic pressure of blood

From the table $P_a = 35,8$, $P_o = 84,2$ means the value of formula

$$A_1 = 64,8 \cdot 84,2 = 5456,16 \text{ ml equal to .}$$

Compute the kinetic energy of blood leaving the left ventricle of the heart

$$A_2 = \frac{m \cdot v^2}{2} = V_y \cdot \rho \cdot \frac{v^2}{2} \quad (4) \text{ .is determined using the (4) formula}$$

Here ρ -blood density. $\rho = 1,050 \text{ kg/m}^3$. v -velocity of blood in the aorta

$$v = 0,4 \text{ m/s}$$

$$A_2 = 5456,16 \cdot 1,050 \cdot \frac{0,4^2}{2} = 458,3174$$

$$A_3 = A_1 + A_2 = 5456,16 + 458,3174 = 5914,477 = 5 \text{ l } 91 \text{ ml}$$

After that, the work of the heart can be found using the following formulae

$$A_i = A_3 + 0,2A_3 = 1,2 \cdot (A_1 + A_2) = 1,2 \cdot (V_y \cdot P_a + \rho \frac{v^2}{2}) \text{ or } A_i = 1,2 \cdot V_y \cdot (P_a + \frac{\rho v^2}{2}) \quad (5)$$

$$A_i = 1,2 \cdot 64,8 \cdot (35,8 + \frac{1,050 \cdot 0,4^2}{2}) = 77,76 \cdot 35,884 = 2790,34 \text{ DJ , or } 3,10 \text{ kg}$$

Normal dynamic pressure is determined using formula (3)

Heart rate cycle $t_{hfr} = \frac{60}{f}$, here f-here f-heart ratez/m

$$f=74 \text{ u/m, } t_{hfr} = \frac{60}{74} = 0,81 \text{ sek}$$

T, which is the time of contraction of the ventricles, is about one third of the duration of the cardiac cycle

$$t = \frac{hfr}{3} = \frac{60}{f} \cdot \frac{1}{3} (s) = \frac{20}{f} = \frac{20}{74} = 0,27 \text{ sek}$$

The output power of the heart during systole

$$N_c = \frac{A_i}{t} = \frac{A_i}{20} \cdot f \quad (6) \quad N_c = \frac{5456,16}{20} = \frac{5456,16}{20} \cdot 74 = 201877,9 \text{ Waat}$$

The minute volume of blood is equal to

$$Q = V_y \cdot f \quad (7) \quad Q = 64,8 \cdot 74 = 4795,2 \text{ litr} = 4 \text{ litres } 79 \text{ ml}$$

These set of equations (1)-(7) form mathematical model of cardiac hemodynamics and allows to assess the state of the state of the cardiovascular system will give.

Systolic and diastolic blood pressure for modeling the cardiovascular system, heart rate and age taken into account. In this case, peaceful state of people and after the action and the indicators are determined by special technologies(1.2-table).

Cardiovascular system was studied among students of 5-22 group of the academic lyceum under Tashkent University of Information Technologies and the results are presented in table (1,2)

Indicators at rest 1-table									
No	Surname. Name	P _s max	P _d min	P _a	P _o	Age	V _y	t=15 sek	t=60 min
1	AbdurakhmonovDonyor	120	80	40	93	16	62,4	17	68
2	AkhadjonovAsilbek	110	70	40	83	16	68,4	20	80
3	AzimjonovaGulshoda	110	70	40	83	16	68,4	20	80
4	KhakimovAsadbek	100	60	40	73	16	74,4	18	72
5	KhasanovBekzod	100	70	0	80	16	63,4	19	76
6	Ma'murjonovaMadina	110	80	30	90	15	58	20	80
7	MirzayevaGulzoda	110	80	30	90	15	58	18	72
8	MukhtorovHurmatillo	120	80	40	93	16	62,4	16	64
9	UrunovOlloberdi	120	0	0	86	16	73,4	17	68
10	KholmatovMashhurbek	90	60	30	70	16	69,4	20	80
11	KholmatovOdiljon	110	80	30	90	16	57,4	22	88
12	YuldashevShakhriyor	100	70	30	80	16	63,4	17	68
n=12	Total	1300	870	430	1011		779	224	896
	Average	108	72,5	35,8	84,25	16	64,9	18,6	74,6

Indicators after physical action .(20 sit-up) 2-table

No	Surname. Name	P _s max	P _d min	P _a	P _o	Age	V _y	t=15 sek	t=60 i
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									n
1	AbdurakhmonovDonyor	13	90	40	103	16	56,4	19	76
2	AkhadjonovAsilbek	130	80	50	96	16	67,4	27	108
3	AzimjonovaGulshoda	130	80	50	96	16	67,4	21	84
4	KhakimovAsadbek	120	80	40	93	16	62,4	22	88
5	KhasanovBekzod	120	80	40	93	16	62,4	21	84
6	Ma'murjonovaMadina	120	90	30	100	15	51,4	20	80
7	MirzayevaGulzoda	120	90	30	100	15	51,4	21	84
8	MukhtorovHurmatillo	130	80	50	96	16	67,4	25	100
9	UrunovOlloberdi	120	90	30	100	16	51,4	22	88
10	KholmatovMashhurbek	120	80	40	93	16	62,4	21	84
11	KholmatovOdiljon	130	90	40	103	16	6,	21	84
12	YuldashevShakhriyor	130	80	50	96	16	67,4	19	76
n=12	Total	1500	1010	490	1173		723,8	259	1036
	Average	125	84	0	97,7	1	60,3	21,5	86,3

Equipment:computer,blood preasure monitor,phonendoscope ,stopwatch

P_s max -the systolic pressure of blood , P_d min-the diastolic pressure of blood
 P_a -the pulse pressure of heart . P_o -the normal blood preasure in aorta
 V_y -the systolic size of heart

According to this python program language, it shows that the action of heart after the physical action’s last results of Abdurakhmonov Doniyor. The heart pressure of another students will be shown with this program.

```
n = int(input("Enter The number of students: "))
fori in range(1, n+1):
name = input(f"{i}-Enter The name and surname of students: ")
p_s = int(input(f"{i}-Enter The systolic blood pressure of students (at rest) "))
```

```

p_d = int(input(f"{i}-Enter The diasystolic blood pressure of students (at rest
"))
p_s2 = int(input(f"{i}-Enter The systolic blood pressure of students (after
physical action): "))
p_d2 = int(input(f"{i}-Enter The diasystolic pressure of blood of students (after
physical action): "))
y = int(input(f"{i}-Enter The age of student: "))
p_a = p_s - p_d #The pulse pressure of heart
p_o = p_d + (p_a/3) #Normal blood pressure in aorta
v_y = 100 + (0.5 * p_a) - (0.6 * p_d) - (0.6 * y) #The systolic size of heart
v = 0.4
p = 1.0502
a1 = v_y * p_o #The amount of blood ejected from The left ventricle
a2 = v_y * p * ((v**2)/2) #Kinetic energy released from The left ventricle
a_i = 1.2 * v_y * (p_a + (p*(v**2)/2)) ##The work of heart

p_a2 = p_s2 - p_d2 #The pulse of pressure of blood
p_o2 = p_d2 + (p_a2/3) #The normal blood pressure in aorta
v_y2 = 100 + (0.5 * p_a2) - (0.6 * p_d2) - (0.6 * y) #The systolic size of heart
a1_2 = v_y2 * p_o2 #The amount of blood ejected from The left ventricle
a2_2 = v_y2 * p * ((v**2)/2) #Kinetic energy released from The left ventricle
a_i2 = 1.2 * v_y2 * (p_a2 + (p*(v**2)/2)) ##The work of heart
print(f"\n{name} measurements in normal situation:\n\
The pulse pressure of heart: {p_a}\n\
The normal blood pressure in aorta: {p_o}\n\
The systolic size of heart: {v_y}\n\
The amount of blood ejected from the left ventricle: {a1}\n\
Kinetic energy realized from the left ventricle: {a2}\n\
The work of heart: {a_i}\n\n\
The measurements after physical action:\n\
The pulse pressure of heart: {p_a2}\n\
The normal blood pressure in aorta: {p_o2}\n\
The systolic size of heart: {v_y2}\n\
The amount of blood ejected from The left ventricle: {a1_2}\n\
Kinetic energy realized from The left ventricle: {a2_2}\n\
The work of heart : {a_i2}")

```

```

1 n = int(input("Enter The number of students: "))
2 for i in range(1, n+1):
3     name = input(f"[{i}] Enter the name and surname of students: ")
4     p_1 = int(input(f"[{i}] Enter the systolic blood pressure of students (at rest): "))
5     p_2 = int(input(f"[{i}] Enter the diastolic blood pressure of students (at rest): "))
6     p_12 = int(input(f"[{i}] Enter The systolic blood pressure of students (after physical action): "))
7     p_22 = int(input(f"[{i}] Enter The diastolic pressure of blood of students (after physical action): "))
8     y = int(input(f"[{i}] Enter The age of student: "))
9     p_s = p_1 - p_2 #The pulse pressure of heart
10    p_0 = p_1 + (p_2/3) #Normal blood pressure in aorta
11    v_1 = 100 + (0.5 * p_1) - (0.8 * p_2) - (0.6 * y) #The systolic size of heart
12    v_2 = 0.4
13    p = 1.0662
14    a1 = v_1 * p_0 #The amount of blood ejected from the left ventricle
15    a2 = v_1 * p * ((v_1**2)/2) #Kinetic energy released from The left ventricle
16    w_1 = 1.2 * v_1 * (a_1 + (p*(v_1**2)/2)) #The work of heart
17
18    p_122 = p_12 - p_22 #The value of pressure of blood
19    p_02 = p_122 + (p_22/3) #The normal blood pressure in aorta
20    v_12 = 100 + (0.5 * p_12) - (0.6 * p_22) - (0.6 * y) #The systolic size of heart
21    v_22 = v_2 * p_02 #The amount of blood ejected from the left ventricle
22    a2_2 = v_22 * p * ((v_22**2)/2) #Kinetic energy released from The left ventricle
23    w_12 = 1.2 * v_22 * (p_02 + (p*(v_22**2)/2)) #The work of heart
24    print(f"[{i}] Measurements in normal situation:\n
25    The pulse pressure of heart: {p_0}\n
26    The normal blood pressure in aorta: {p_02}\n
27    The systolic size of heart: {v_1}\n
28    The amount of blood ejected from the left ventricle: {a1}\n
29    Kinetic energy released from the left ventricle: {a2}\n
30    The work of heart: {w_1}\n\n
31    The measurements after physical action:\n
32    The pulse pressure of heart: {p_02}\n
33    The normal blood pressure in aorta: {p_022}\n
34    The systolic size of heart: {v_12}\n
35    The amount of blood ejected from the left ventricle: {a12}\n
36    Kinetic energy released from the left ventricle: {a2_2}\n

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